

LEGAL SYSTEM OF COUNTERING EXTREMISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article provides a legal analysis of countering religious extremism and proposals for improving legislation.

Key words: extremism, concept of extremism, international extremism, problem of extremism, religious extremism.

At the turn of the century, extremism is no longer an occasional and extraordinary phenomenon. In the modern world, it has become a widely practiced method of forceful resolution of a number of acute problems by various religious, political, and nationalist movements. Extremism in recent years has acquired a global character, threatening the interests of citizens, public security, the stability of countries and international relations. Threats of international extremism today remain a pressing problem in Central Asia, which requires constant attention [1, p. 456-460].

It is obvious that countering extremism is becoming one of the main tasks of ensuring national security for any country, regardless of its geographical location, size of territory, population, or economic status.

Events in the world have highlighted the international nature of extremism, necessitating a reevaluation of pre-existing notions about it as a global threat, given that extremism ranks among the most significant issues facing the entire modern world community. The events of recent years show that today there are no countries in which various kinds of conflicts are not considered as manifestations of extremism, usually on religious or ethnic grounds.

It should be noted that according to the definition given by the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe in 2003, "extremism is a form of political activity that directly or indirectly rejects the principles of parliamentary democracy" [2, p. 25].

Undoubtedly, the intensification of extremist activity in multi-ethnic Uzbekistan has the character of a threat to its security and socio-political stability. Therefore, one of the main tasks of the authorities and law enforcement agencies is to counter manifestations of extremism, to form in young people attitudes of tolerant consciousness and behavior, and to achieve civil peace and harmony in society.

An essential condition that could prevent the growth of extremism and contribute to a more successful fight against it is the harmonization of national legislation with international standards, of course, taking into account the peculiarities of our national legislation.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, solemnly proclaiming its commitment to human rights and freedoms, national and universal values, and the principles of country sovereignty, reaffirming its fidelity to the ideals of democracy, freedom and equality, social justice, and solidarity, states that human rights and freedoms are recognized and guaranteed in the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the generally recognized rules of

international law. Democracy in Uzbekistan is based on universal principles, according to which the supreme value is the human being, his or her life, freedom, honor, dignity, and other inalienable rights. As President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev noted in his congratulatory message: “In the new constitutional conditions, we will continue our reforms to ensure the interests of the human being, his honor, and dignity with even greater determination. In accordance with the will of our people, we must fully realize in practice the principles enshrined in the Main Law and make them an integral part of our lives” [3].

In accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, all citizens have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law, regardless of sex, race, nationality, language, religion, beliefs, social origin or social status (part 2, article 19) [4]. Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, speech, and beliefs. Everyone has the right to seek, receive, and disseminate any information (part 2, article 33).

At the same time, the Constitution proceeds from the fact that the exercise of human and civil rights and freedoms must not violate the rights and freedoms of other persons, society, and the country (part 2, article 21).

Of course, it should be noted that restrictions on the right to seek, receive, and disseminate information are permitted only in accordance with the law and only to the extent necessary to protect the constitutional order, public health, public morals, and the rights and freedoms of others; to ensure public security and public order; and to prevent the disclosure of country secrets or other secrets protected by law (part 4, article 21).

However, it should be emphasized that the establishment and activities of political parties and other non-governmental non-profit organizations with the aim of changing the constitutional order by force, opposing country sovereignty and the territorial integrity and security of Uzbekistan, propagating war, social, ethnic, racial, or religious hatred, and infringing constitutional rights and freedoms, public health, or public morals, as well as political parties, are prohibited. The establishment of secret societies and associations is prohibited (article 71).

Undoubtedly, an important event in the republic was the adoption of the law “On Countering Extremist Activity” on July 30, 2018, which for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan designed a mechanism to counter extremism in general, rather than its individual types and forms [5]. Article 3 of the Law “On Countering Extremist Activity” defines extremist activity (extremism) as the activity of planning, organizing, preparing, or committing actions aimed at:

Forcible change of the foundations of the constitutional order, violation of the territorial integrity and sovereignty of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

–Seizure or appropriation of power;

–Establishment of or participation in illegal armed groups;

–Carrying out terrorist activities;

–Incitement to national, racial, ethnic, or religious hatred, incitement to national, racial, ethnic, or religious hatred associated with violence or public calls to violence;

–Production, possession, distribution, or demonstration of materials containing a threat to public security or public order, or production, possession, distribution or demonstration of the paraphernalia or symbols of extremist organizations;

-The organization of mass riots motivated by political, ideological, racial, national, ethnic or religious hatred or enmity against a social group or a religious organization; or enmity against a social group, etc.

In this regard, identifying the most effective measures aimed at warning and preventing extremism, eliminating sources and channels of their financing, and combining national and international efforts in this area is one of the important directions of state policy, and in order to improve measures to counter extremism and terrorism, the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Countering Extremism and Terrorism for 2021 - 2026 and the "Roadmap" for the implementation of the National Strategy were approved. It should be noted that one of the priority directions of the strategy is to improve the legal framework in the sphere of countering extremism and terrorism [6].

The leading role in ensuring counteraction to extremism, among other legal ways, belongs to criminal-legal means. This circumstance has led to a special importance of distinguishing extremist crimes. Their public danger is characterized by their ability to cause substantial harm to such important objects of legal protection as the foundations of the constitutional order and the constitutional foundations of interpersonal relations.

The following amendments have been made to the Special part of the Criminal Code.

The terms "religious extremist" and "religious organizations" have been used in the disposition of article 244¹, paragraph one; the disposition of article 244¹, paragraph two; and the disposition of article 244², paragraph one.

Article 244². ("Establishment, leadership, participation in religious extremist, separatist, fundamentalist, or other prohibited organizations"): Establishment, leadership, participation in religious extremist, separatist, fundamentalist, or other prohibited organizations.

Also, the disposition of Article 246, Contraband contains the concept of extremism. Note "religious extremism", i.e., again we are talking only about religious extremism.

Extremism is becoming an obstacle to achieving civil accord, strengthening democratic values, and ensuring security in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In our view, the state authorities must consistently ensure constitutional rights guaranteeing the equality of citizens of any race and ethnicity and freedom of conscience. All existing laws should be subjected to expert review, and laws and other normative legal acts to counter extremism should be developed and adopted. In order to resolve the above-mentioned problems, we consider it necessary to amend the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the sphere of countering extremist activity, and special attention should be paid to the very concept of "extremism" and "extremist activity", since it is on the clarity of definitions of these terms in the law that the effectiveness of the application of all legislation in the sphere of countering extremism largely depends. It seems to us that the existing set of signs of extremism in the Law "On countering extremist activity" no longer fully corresponds to the new threats and challenges facing the state and society at present. We agree with the opinion that it is the clarity of definitions of these terms in the law that largely determines the quality of all legislation in the field of countering extremism and, consequently, the effectiveness of law enforcement activities.

It also seems advisable to amend the dispositions of part one of article 244¹, disposition of part two of article 244¹, as well as the dispositions of part one of article 244², to leave only "extremist" instead of "religious extremist" and "extremist religious organizations", as well as

to make additions excluding the possibility of applying statutes of limitations for persons convicted of extremist crimes.

Thus, preventing extremism is an extremely complex task, as this phenomenon is generated by many social, political, psychological, economic, historical, and other reasons. The fight against such phenomena as extremism should be as effective as possible at the legislative level; it is necessary to improve and enhance the legislation regulating the fight against extremism.

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